

**SYNTHESIS GROWTH STRUCTURAL SPECTROSCOPIC AND OPTICAL
PROPERTIES OF L-LYSINE SODIUM CHLORIDE NON LINEAR OPTICAL
CRYSTALS**

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Semi-organic non linear optical material of L-Lysine Sodium chloride was grown by slow evaporation technique at room temperature. Single crystal XRD was carried out to examine the crystal system and unit cell parameters. Powder XRD a pattern confirms the basic structure of materials and the functional groups was identified by using FTIR spectrum. TG/DTA analysis is confirms that the stability of grown crystals. The transparency of grown crystals was analysed by UV-VIS-NIR. The second harmonic generation (SHG) conversion efficiency has been estimated and the output power of the crystal was determined by using Kurtz powder technique.

Key words; Crystal growth; Slow evaporation technique; -Lysine Sodium chloride

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